

VITAMIN D AND AGING

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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4237-1158>**Abstract**

Aging affects the formation of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25[OH]₂D; calcitriol), the active form of vitamin D. Production of 1,25(OH)₂D is reduced by 50% as a result of an age-related decline in renal function, although serum 1,25(OH)₂D levels are maintained in part by secondary hyperparathyroidism. Aging also causes a decrease in calcium absorption that precedes the decrease in 1,25(OH)₂D by 10 to 15 years. Because 1,25(OH)₂D is dependent on an adequate supply of the substrate vitamin D, the development of vitamin D deficiency leads to further reduction in the formation of 1,25(OH)₂D. Measurement of the metabolite 25OHD provides the most widely used assessment of vitamin D deficiency. A serum 25OHD level lower than 10 ng/mL (25 nmol/L) represents vitamin D deficiency and leads to a reduction in serum 1,25(OH)₂D. Vitamin D deficiency, is uncommon in North America, probably because of supplementation of dairy products and other foods with vitamin D. Sunlight exposure increases serum 25OHD levels by about 10 ng/mL during the months of April through September, resulting in low serum 25OHD for about 3 to 4 months in winter, with 2 additional months of low levels in more northern latitudes, such as Canada, and 2 fewer months in the southern states. Vitamin D supplementation in the winter can prevent vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D insufficiency has been defined by the Institute of Medicine as a serum 25OHD level lower than 20 ng/mL (and >10 ng/mL). A serum 25OHD level lower than 20 ng/mL is associated with an increased fracture rate and increased rate of bone loss and treatment. Although other diseases have been associated with low serum 25OHD levels, the evidence for a causative role has not yet been established. Treatment of elderly people with vitamin D 800 IU daily will increase serum 25OHD levels to higher than 20 ng/mL and reduce fractures; this is particularly important in institutionalized people.

Keywords: Vitamin D metabolism, Aging, Vitamin D insufficiency, Vitamin D treatment.

Vitamin D metabolism

Vitamin D is derived from diet and sunlight and is not biologically active. Vitamin D must be sequentially converted into 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25OHD) in the

liver by the enzyme CYP2R1 and then into 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25[OH]₂D) in the kidney by the CYP27B1 enzyme (1 α hydroxylase) (Fig. 1). Both 1,25(OH)₂D and 25OHD are carried in the circulation by vitamin D-binding protein (DBP).

Fig. 1.

The active hormonal form of vitamin D is 1,25(OH)₂D, which binds to the vitamin D receptor (VDR) together with the retinoid X receptor to activate specific genes in target organs.¹ VDR is present in many tissues besides bone, and certain cells, such as immune and osteoprogenitor cells, also contain the 1 α hydroxylase enzyme as part of an intracrine and paracrine system. The regulation of the 1 α hydroxylase enzyme is tightly maintained so as to keep serum 1,25(OH)₂D levels constant. Production of 1,25(OH)₂D is upregulated by parathyroid hormone (PTH) and low serum phosphorus and inhibited by fibroblast growth factor (FGF-23), which also regulates serum phosphorus levels. The enzyme CYP24 hydroxylase converts 25OHD to the nonactive metabolite 24,25(OH)₂D in the kidney, thereby limiting the production of 1,25(OH)₂D. Local formation of 24,25(OH)₂D is also induced in many target tissues through negative feedback by 1,25(OH)₂D.

1,25(OH)₂D is essential for the efficient absorption of dietary calcium and phosphorus and for mineralization of bone. Recently, 1,25(OH)₂D has been recognized to have a multitude of other biologic functions. Studies suggest that it is unlikely that serum 25OHD has an independent physiologic function that is not fulfilled by 1,25(OH)₂D.

Effect of age and vitamin D on calcium metabolism

The following are effects of age on vitamin D and calcium metabolism:

- Decreased calcium absorption
- Intestinal resistance of calcium absorption to circulating 1,25(OH)₂D
- Decreased VDR
- Decreased renal production of 1,25(OH)₂D by the aging kidney
- Decreased skin production of vitamin D
- Substrate deficiency of vitamin D

Decreased Calcium Absorption

Malabsorption of calcium occurs as part of aging and starts at approximately age 65 to 70 years.^{2,3} As a result, it leads to negative calcium balance, secondary

hyperparathyroidism, increased bone loss, and osteoporosis. Because of malabsorption of calcium, there is a decreased ability to adapt to a low-calcium diet by increasing fractional calcium absorption.⁴ Although several independent dietary factors affect calcium absorption, such as protein intake, sodium intake, or glucose, the main regulator is 1,25(OH)₂D acting through the VDR and synthesizing genes and proteins involved in calcium transport.⁵ Deletion of the VDR results in malabsorption of calcium.⁶ Calcium absorption occurs by both an active saturable system and a passive diffusion transport system. Active transport of calcium occurs through transcellular and paracellular pathways in the duodenum and jejunum, whereas passive paracellular absorption is the main process of calcium absorption throughout the intestine.⁷ At the molecular level, the calcium-binding protein calbindin-D9k and an epithelial calcium channel transient receptor potential vanilloid type 6 (TRPV6) were initially thought to mediate the diffusion of calcium across the gut.⁷⁻⁹ However, in TRPV6/Calbindin-D9k double knockout mice, calcium absorption still responds to 1,25(OH)₂D administration, challenging this mechanism.¹⁰ The tight junction proteins Claudins-2 and Claudins-12 facilitate paracellular calcium transport and are upregulated by 1,25(OH)₂D via the VDR receptor.¹¹ In summary, part of the change in calcium absorption with aging may be because of abnormalities in the transport proteins that are regulated by 1,25(OH)₂D.

Intestinal Resistance of Calcium Absorption to Circulating 1,25(OH)₂D

In young healthy people, there is a positive correlation between calcium absorption and serum 1,25(OH)₂D, but in older people and patients with osteoporosis, the calcium absorption response is lower relative to serum 1,25(OH)₂D than in young people (Fig. 2), suggesting intestinal resistance to endogenous circulating 1,25(OH)₂D.^{12,13} However, administration of a small oral dose of calcitriol 0.25 μ g twice daily to elderly people completely normalizes malabsorption of calcium, suggesting that calcitriol may have a first-pass effect on intestinal transport.¹⁴

Fig. 2.

Decreased VDR

Aging may affect the intestinal concentration of VDR to cause a decrease in calcium absorption, as demonstrated in aging rats.¹⁵ There have been 2 studies of intestinal VDR performed on biopsies in humans. A small study of 9 subjects older than 65 years Vitamin D and Aging 321 showed a decrease in intestinal VDR concentration with age but no change in serum 1,25(OH)₂D.¹⁶ In a similar study of 41 women older than 65, 10 of whom were older than 75, there was no difference in intestinal VDR concentration compared with 59 women younger than 35.¹⁷

Decreased Renal Production of 1,25(OH)₂D by the Aging Kidney

As renal function declines with age, there is a decrease in the activity of the renal enzyme 1 α hydroxylase that converts 25OHD into 1,25(OH)₂D. Serum 1,25(OH)₂D levels are inversely related to serum creatinine and glomerular function rate (GFR) and a GFR of 50 mL/min is a level that affects 1,25(OH)₂D production.¹⁸ Because many people older than 80 have a GFR less than 50 mL/min, decreased production of 1,25(OH)₂D in this age group is common. To examine the effect of age and GFR on the 25OHD-1,25(OH)₂D axis, we infused PTH for 24 hours in women of different ages. The increase in serum 1,25(OH)₂D was about 50% lower in the older subjects, indicating decreased renal responsiveness to PTH with age (Fig. 3).¹⁹

Fig. 3.

Measurement of serum 1,25(OH)₂D in elderly people shows the impact clinically of declining renal production. In a study of women aged 80 to 95 years who were residents of nursing homes and had normal 25OHD levels, the serum 1,25(OH)₂D levels were much lower than in women aged 65 to 75 years (Fig. 4). In summary,

There is an age-related decrease in calcium absorption that is partly dependent and partly independent of 1,25(OH)₂D.

Serum 1,25(OH)₂D levels decrease as a result of an age-related decline in renal function.

Reduced levels of serum 1,25(OH)₂D likely further reduce calcium absorption, causing secondary hyperparathyroidism and increased bone resorption.

Secondary hyperparathyroidism persistently stimulates renal 1,25(OH)₂D production until the kidney can no longer respond effectively.

Fig. 4.

Decreased Skin Production

Aging reduces vitamin D production in skin. There is a decrease in the concentration of 7-dehydrocholesterol in the epidermis in old compared with young individuals and a reduced response to UV light, resulting in a 50% decrease in the formation of previtamin D₃.²⁰

Substrate Deficiency of Vitamin D

All age-related changes in vitamin D metabolism are magnified if there is concomitant vitamin D deficiency, because it limits the substrate supply for 25OHD and ultimately 1,25(OH)₂D. Substrate deficiency is a common problem in the elderly and is important to recognize because it is preventable and treatable. There may be deficiency of vitamin D either from diet or from lack of sunlight, and the decrease in serum 25OHD further limits 1,25(OH)₂D production, especially when there is also renal dysfunction. Serum

1,25(OH)₂D levels decrease when serum the 25OHD level falls below 10 ng/mL in both younger²¹ and older²² people.

Vitamin D nutrition in the elderly

Vitamin D is a unique nutrient because its requirement is met from diet and skin. The dietary intake of vitamin D can be estimated from dietary food tables and is usually between 100 and 400 IU daily. Dietary surveys in North America in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) show that dietary intake of vitamin D is low, averaging 200 IU daily (Table 1), and, unless one eats a lot of fish with high vitamin D content, daily intake is unlikely to exceed 400 IU daily. Vitamin D intake increases with age because elderly people consume more multivitamins that contain vitamin D.^{23,24}

Table 1.

Vitamin D intake and serum 25 hydroxyvitamin D (25OHD) for the United States, 2005–2006

Age Group (y)	Vitamin D Intake (IU/d) (mean \pm SE)		Serum 25OHD ng/mL (mean \pm SE)
	Diet Alone ^a	Total Intake ^b	
Males			
14–18	244 \pm 16	276 \pm 20	24 \pm 0.6
19–30	204 \pm 12	264 \pm 16	23 \pm 0.5
31–50	216 \pm 12	316 \pm 12	24 \pm 0.4
51–70	204 \pm 12	352 \pm 16	24 \pm 0.5
>70	224 \pm 16	428 \pm 28	24 \pm 0.4
Females			
14–18	152 \pm 8	200 \pm 20	24 \pm 0.7
19–30	144 \pm 12	232 \pm 12	25 \pm 0.8
31–50	176 \pm 12	308 \pm 20	23 \pm 0.5
51–70	156 \pm 16	404 \pm 40	23 \pm 0.4
>70	180 \pm 8	400 \pm 20	23 \pm 0.4

The production of vitamin D in skin cannot be measured directly; however, the change in serum 25OHD gives an estimate of the effect of sun if diet remains constant. In the Midwest at latitude 40°, serum 25OHD increases by 50% from 20 to 30 ng/mL in summer²⁵; this change is equivalent to a daily oral vitamin D dose of 2000 IU daily. The UV spectrum is effective only when the sun is more than 30° above the horizon. Below that level, ground pollution filters out the UV rays. In the Midwestern section of North America, effective UV light occurs only between late April and early September. Effective UV exposure time is 2 months less in Canada and 2 months more in Florida. Vitamin D supplementation should be increased in winter.

SUMMARY

Age-related changes affect vitamin D metabolism and reduce the nutritional status of the elderly. A vitamin D supplement is recommended in the elderly. The optimal total calcium intake is unclear. In the absence of adequate safety data, it is suggested that total calcium intake be limited to 1000 to 1200 mg daily, because of a 35% incidence of hypercalciuria or hypercalcemia in women taking low doses of vitamin D who have a total calcium intake of 1200 mg daily.³⁹ Increasing calcium from dietary sources may be safer than supplements, and requires increasing the intake of dairy products or other vitamin D and calcium-fortified foods. The RDA value is listed on every food and vitamin either as the actual amount or as a percentage of the RDA. For example, if the RDA for vitamin D is 800 IU and a multivitamin contains 1000 IU, the multivitamin provides 125% of the RDA. It has been common practice to supplement dairy products in the United States, Canada, and Scandinavian countries. In North America, milk is fortified with 400 IU per quart. An 8-oz glass of milk provides 80 IU of vitamin D and 250

mg calcium. Evidence suggests that vitamin D and calcium nutrition can be improved in the elderly by increasing the vitamin D intake to 800 IU daily together with calcium 1000 mg daily. This combination is a simple inexpensive strategy that can reduce fractures in institutionalized individuals by 30%.

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